

The Quantum Color of Sound

Hen Haim Ben Evgi

¹Fachbereich Physik and Dahlem Center for Complex Quantum Systems- Freie Universitat Berlin
Arnimallee 14- 14195 - Berlin - Germany

Abstract. *The theory of measurement with white and colored noise operators is discussed, utilizing the Collision Model representation of weak continuous measurement. While the former embodies an ideal measurement, the latter admits correlations between pointer states at different times, as it embodies a quantum delay line. The response of this apparatus is shown to be equivalent to a sort of comb filter. We apply these measurements to a simplified scheme for the process of musical sensing. While the measurement with white noise leads to a monotone rise in the certainty of a specific sound, measuring with colored noise introduces several patterns in the output, which we term as the quantum color of the sound and propose several sonifications of the outcome. Much like how feedback delay networks in digital acoustic models create the richness of simulated spaces, our quantum sensor introduces temporal correlations to sound perception through coherent feedback mechanism. Under the speculation that the human ear is sensitive to such temporal correlations, measurement with colored noise could be used to charge a sound signal with rhythmic meaning.*

1 Introduction

A significant portion of the confusion and fascination drawn by the theory of quantum mechanics stems from its measurement postulate, introducing randomness to the outcome of observation - as the result of a single shot measurement is intrinsically unpredictable. It further admits a sort of bias, since the observer inevitably sets a preferred basis for the measurement results [1]. The measurement problem - namely, the heterogeneity of the measurement process to the rest of the theory - still stands, and no dynamical law of a quantum system can explain the process of selection of one result.

Notable progress in demystifying the measurement process was gained by the progress in the study of open quantum systems (OQS). Within the theory of OQS, the apparatus is described as an additional quantum system - the environment. It is the entanglement between the system and the apparatus that leads to the evolution of the original system state - including superpositions that cannot appear under any actual measurement - to decay into a classical state [2]. This process is termed decoherence. Also the dynamical laws of OQS cannot account for the random selection of a single result, and for the most part it is used to study the predictable quantity of the expectation value of multiple measurements. Nevertheless, the random selection is not foreign to OQS, and is in fact used as a method to reproduce the evolution of an open quantum system even when the environment is not an apparatus and no measurement is taking place. One simply represents the environment as

an apparatus and measures with it the system to create a measurement sequence (quantum trajectory [3]), repeating the procedure until convergence yields the evolution of the OQS.

An elegant formalism to OQS as such, and their equivalence to the process of measurement, is the Collision Model [3]. Under which, the environment is represented as an independent set of auxiliary sub-systems, interacting with the system one by one. Both ideal measurements and more realistic settings hold an intuitive representation via the collision model formalism.

In this paper, we will focus on one such setting, in which the memory of the apparatus cannot be neglected. Where an ideal measurement is forgetful, such that the result of the current measurement is independent of the previous one, an apparatus with memory causes a certain bias, conditioning the results in time t to that in time $t-\tau$, where τ is the apparatus memory time. The evolution of an OQS under an environment with non-negligible memory is termed non-Markovian (NM), as opposed to the Markovian evolution induced by an ideal measurement. NM evolution is gaining increased interest in the field of OQS, where the additional complexity is no longer considered as just an obstacle but as offering a computational advantage [4] [5]. We will highlight two features of our NM apparatus: the coherent feedback it imposes on the open quantum system, and its spectral response of a sort of delay filter, with equidistant permitted frequencies.

In applying these models to the realm of quantum music, we suggest a scenario where a sound with a specific frequency - a normal mode - is measured by an apparatus with and without memory. We acknowledge that associating this quantum measurement to the human ear requires a great deal of simplification, thus restricts the results of our analysis to the following speculation: what if the human ear were to measure sound with a quantum measurement. We will posit this speculation within current theories of consciousness, and utilize it to define our notion of quantum color of sound- the characters of the output sound resulting from a measurement with colored noise.

This quantum color of a sound further motivated our speculation by intriguing parallels to established approaches in digital audio. Just as the Ball within the Box (BaBo) model uses feedback delay networks to create realistic acoustic simulations [6], a colored noise measurement employs a delay line performing a quantum coherent feedback [7] that generates similar effects on the output sound (the sound perceived by a listener). In both cases, a comb filter-like spectral response emerges [8] [6], and thus a colored noise quantum measurement in the human hearing process could fulfill a similar role (of predicting the actual sound from minimal amount of information, as common in prominent theories of human perception [9]). We note that

the quantum characteristics of delayed measurement introduce non-classical correlations that have no direct counterpart in traditional acoustic modeling. These quantum-specific features- if were to be present in the product of human listening, could offer novel approaches to understanding musical structure and how temporal patterns in sound acquire perceptual meaning. At this point, we merely highlight the potential of a quantum delay-line (our colored noise apparatus) in achieving these types of sound modulation, leaving these possible consequences for future development.

Our paper is organized as follows. In section 2 we will utilize QQS theory to introduce our two measurement processes; Measuring with white noise resulting in ideal measurement, and measuring with colored noise, introducing memory effects in the output. In section 3 we will define our model of auditory perception and within it apply our two measurements. We have experimented with realization of the QQS simulating these apparatuses along with various sonifications of the output. The resulting color of perceived sound will be discussed with respect to assumptions incorporated into our auditory perception model. We explore a specific sonification of the output (determining our conversion of quantum states into sound). From which, we define the color of the sound via the fingerprint of the colored measurement. Where the representation of the output in our chosen sonification highlight a certain feature of the memory effects, we mention an alternative in the outlook, along with the resulting definition of the quantum color it imprints over the measured sound.

2 Quantum measurement with noise

2.1 Principles of the model

Figure 1: The interaction scheme in the quantum collision model. A system S initialized in a state ρ_0 and an environment composed of independent auxiliary units in state η , "colliding" with the system one by one, by a sequence of unitary interactions U_m between the system and the m-th auxiliary unit. Taken from [3]

One of the troubling characteristics of the quantum measurement is its invasive nature. A way to reduce it is by constructing a continuous measurement. With which,

the measurement is performed over a finite time, that is split into effectively infinitesimal time steps. In every time step, the system interacts with a "fresh" auxiliary subsystem - that is initialized in the ground state and is uncorrelated to the system. The system-auxiliary interaction is set to be weak, such that upon measuring the auxiliary unit only partial information on the system is gained, thus only modestly altering the system's state. Therefore, throughout the measurement, the system is continuously monitored by this repeated interaction with a stream of auxiliary units, until sufficient certainty of the result is gained.

The apparatus operates here precisely as the environment in the quantum collision model (see figure 1). It is composed of a chain of independent units colliding with the system one by one. Regardless of whether they are measured or not, the evolution they induce on the system is Markovian - typically a monotone decay of excitation or coherence. The equivalence between the evolution with or without measurement is apparent when averaging over all possible results. The expectation value of all possible measurement sequences is identical to that where the system only collides with the auxiliary units but no measurement takes place. Presented formally, the joint state of the system plus auxiliaries $|\phi_n\rangle$ will be after the n -th interaction [3]:

$$|\phi_n\rangle = \sum_{\alpha_n, \dots, \alpha_1} \hat{K}_{\alpha_n} \dots \hat{K}_{\alpha_1} \{ |S_0\rangle \} \otimes |\alpha_1\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |\alpha_n\rangle \quad (1)$$

The right hand side of the equation can signify a sequence of measurements - with measurement operators K_{α_m} (where α_m is the result) - and the sum over $\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n$ that runs over all combinations of measurements results. Alternatively, it is merely a sequence of interactions between the system and the collision model environment, where the effective measurement operator is defined by the interaction as $\hat{K}_{\alpha_m} \equiv \langle \alpha_m | U_m | \eta \rangle$. A measurement-less measurement if you wish, where typical traits of measurement - such as decoherence - still apply to the system evolution, just without a collapse into one measurement result.

In this work, we will focus on the latter, thus regard the result of a sound measurement via the evolution of the system and the auxiliary units - the pointers in our setting. Therefore, an apparatus will be defined foremost by the evolution it induces, where we keep in mind that this evolution could be constructed from the average of multiple measurement sequences. This choice will be motivated in the next section.

2.2 White noise

The collision model presented in the previous section emerges from the input-output formalism [10]. Under which, our measurement setting is described as a system plugged in with a white noise channel, that weakly alters the system state (for example - decohere the purity of the initial state). Upon measuring the output of this channel, information about the original state of the system can be gained. See figure 2 for illustration.

The emergence argument relies on an initial picture of a

Figure 2: The resulting evolution of the system due to interaction with white noise apparatus.

system interacting with an environment composed of a continuum of harmonic oscillators (Bosonic modes). On the condition of a weak interaction between the system and each of the harmonic oscillators, one can safely assume the system interacts equally with all harmonic oscillators [3]. This allows both the representation of the environment modes in time domain - via the Fourier transform of the harmonic oscillators - and the discretization of these time modes into auxiliary sub-systems [11]. Their interaction with the system is independent since their operators are delta-correlated to one another, thus termed white noise operators.

We outlined this argument to highlight that every auxiliary unit represents harmonic oscillators in all frequencies. The effective frequency response of the apparatus - which we identify as the spectral density of the environment [2] - is assumed by the emergence argument to be flat, yielding a delta function in the time representation of the system-apparatus coupling. It assures that no memory effects are induced, thus allowing an ideal measurement.

2.3 Colored noise

The same path can be generalized for the case of colored noise. The channel is still composed of an input of white noise (independent auxiliary units) and an output where measurement takes place. The difference lies in the collision structure, that is no longer bound to one by one, allowing multiple collisions in a single time step.

Arguably the simplest deviation from this structure is a delay setting, where in every time step the system collides with two auxiliaries - a fresh one and a delayed one. We thus construct an apparatus out of a quantum delay line. It is injected with fresh auxiliaries, and collides them with the system one by one. After the first collision, the auxiliary is wired to a delay line - in which its quantum state collects a phase - and at the end of it collides with the system again. Only then it can be measured for an output.

This setting creates correlations between the measurement results at different times - specifically those which occurs at a time difference in the length of the delay. These correlations are incorporated into the evolution of the system and create collective effects. An example of the resulting evolution is given in figure 3. If we were to measure the auxiliary units as they leave the channel, even

Figure 3: Evolution of a system interacting with a collision model with delay. The delay and the phase are kept fixed (to constructive feedback). Each plot matches different interaction strength (compare to figure 2). In all cases, the evolution is not monotone, as a result of memory effects.

upon averaging the results to time steps far larger than the time scale of the delay, the measurements will be explicitly dependent on the results of those prior to them ($P_{\alpha_m}(|S_{m-1}\rangle, \alpha_{m-1})$). This collision model also emerges from an environment of harmonic oscillators [12]. This time the spectral density (frequency response) is not flat. It's form depends on the delay (τ) and phase (ϕ) - where a phase of 0 or π will induce coherent feedback over the evolution of the system [7].

This type of setting is more than an idealization chosen for its convenient spectral density, but can be constructed empirically by a semi-infinite waveguide [13], i.e., a waveguide with a mirror in one of its edges. This physical setting is in turn equivalent to a multicavity [8], whose frequency response (spectral density) is a sum of Lorentzian functions, centered around frequencies with difference proportional to the inverse of the delay. Thus, it embodies a sort of comb filter (see figure 4). Note that also the quality of the filter (how narrow the Lorentzians) scales with the inverse of the delay. The comb filter-like frequency response (multi-cavity) and the temporal correlations in the output (collision model with delay) are adjoint representations of the same phenomena (similarly to the time and frequency domain of the same signal).

3 Application in auditory perception

Relating quantum behavior to consciousness is neither new [14] nor foreign to empirical research [15]. In consciousness-collapse theories, consciousness is introduced as the missing piece for solving the measurement problem, and similarly quantum information is utilized as a remedy for the hard problem of consciousness¹ [16].

In our approach, we begin by assuming that quantum phenomena appear in nature in macroscopic scales, and further assume that perceived quantum information can affect the collective state of consciousness (the conscious experience). If so, then a quantum measurement ought to take

¹The hard problem amounts to- how could experience arise from scientific mechanisms, or simply the longstanding mind-body problem

Figure 4: Illustration of the spectral density of the multi-cavity emerging from the collision model with delay. The three plots are for three different phases. For feedback phases: $\phi = 0$ or π , the peaks are placed separated by the frequency difference $\Delta\omega = 2\pi/\tau$ from one another. For $\phi = \pi/2$: $\Delta\omega = \pi/\tau$ with amplitudes smaller by a factor of $1/\sqrt{2}$ compared to the feedback case. In all cases, the width of the Lorentzians is fixed by $\gamma = 2/\tau$.

place in the sensory system.

When applied to the notion of quantum music, our claim is that some characteristics of quantum sound (as the one generated by the quantum drums [17]) hold musical meaning (in the same way that the classical character of wavelength ratios holds a meaning such as the perfect-fifth).

In the light of this hypothesis, we will introduce our quantum measurement schemes to the human auditory system, and interpret the output sound as not only the product of quantum computation but the quantum character of perceived sound. This approach suffers (as most quantum theories of consciousness) from the difficulty to sustain coherence of quantum information in relevant scales. Nevertheless, since quantum laws hold no limitation in principle, we believe that naturalistic theories of consciousness will sooner or later overcome this obstacle, and utilize the advantage of quantum computation (over classical computation) to explain that performed by consciousness. Until such a theory matures into a feasible physical realization, the following is no more than an exploration for the role such quantum sound measurements could satisfy.

3.1 The model

Putting these measurement schemes in practice, we represent a sound wave by a quantum harmonic oscillator with frequency Ω (a normal/Bosonic mode). For simplicity, we restrict our model to a two-level system, allowing us to represent this state via a qubit. The excited state is taken as a sine wave with frequency Ω . We omit handling of phases, since assigning a definite meaning to the ground state and the superposition will already leave enough room for different sonifications of the measured sound.

When the sound frequency is known to the observer before the measurement, neither of our schemes is the ideal

choice, since instantaneous quantum measurement can be constructed [18]. When the sound frequency is unknown, then determining it to a precision of $\Delta\omega$ requires total time of measurement that scales with $1/\Delta\omega$, as a result of the time energy uncertainty relation. Here, our schemes become relevant.

We ignore the question of how the frequency is determined and merely assume that it's done such that we can determine the frequency Ω to a precision of $\Delta\omega$, denoted as $\tilde{\Omega}$. Thus we focus on applying both schemes to determine if the sound is there or not - meaning, if the quantum state is excited. The graphs of typical evolution of the state due to interaction with white noise and colored noise apparatus are presented in figures 2 and 3 respectively.

We highlight that these evolutions are but the average results of an actual measurement taking place. Support for considering them as the relevant quantity is given by the following argument: Consider a sound propagating into a quantum sensor. The sensor will interact with the quantized form of the wave (the phonons). They will be measured one by one, and a stable output will thus be the average result of the measurement of each of the waves.

This choice will allow us to distinguish more easily the difference between white noise and colored noise output (instead of the tedious task of distinguishing two random trajectories - one with and one without non-local correlations). Since both the colored and white input are now deterministic, so will be our following notion of the quantum color of sound.

To conclude, our general framework involves taking a sine wave with a certain audible frequency, representing it as a quantum two level system (qubit) and measure it with three different schemes- a white noise measurement, measurement with delay, and measurement through a multicavity. The expectation value of the output is then converted back into sound by using the output as an envelope for the input sound. Therefore, we effectively sonify the excitation of the output as the amplitude of the output sound. Note that though the delay scheme and multicavity scheme are equivalent (yield the same evolution on the system), our procedure will yield different audio outputs- where in delay one (as in the white noise), a single envelope is produced for the sound wave with the input frequency, in the multicavity case an output is calculated for each of the cavities, from which an envelope for the frequency of that cavity is produced (where one of the cavities is the resonant cavity- with an equal frequency to the input [8]). The physical parameters required to set any of these schemes are the delay, phase and measurement strength (system-CM coupling), from which can be derived also the multicavity parameters.

We've implemented these schemes with a quantum simulation on a classical computer using QuTiP library [19], as a result, we've limited the amount of two level systems that participate in the evolution to 11, yielding a restriction of 9 qubits for the delay line. Then, in order to simulate distinguishable delays- determined by the amount of qubits in the delay line times the time step of our discrete evolution- we needed to restrict our quantum measurement to sam-

pling rate of the order of 100Hz. As a consequence, in sonifying the output we needed to perform time interpolation, converting the quantum output to 220,000 audio samples. In addition, the 11 qubits threshold forces also the approximation of 5 cavities when representing the delay line in the equivalent multi-cavity picture. As an outcome of these approximations, we sometimes took the liberty of mapping an input frequency to a lower frequency of the quantum state, in order to reach the parameter space where quantum coherent feedback creates rich evolutions within our computational resources.

We present here a sample of the core of the algorithm- the trotterization of the evolution of the joint system (S-R-M-E, system-cavity-modes-delay line-fresh auxiliary unit) into discrete time steps, while calculating the expectation value of the excitation of auxiliary units leaving the delay line:

3.2 Code Sample

Code 1: Evolution of system+apparatus

```

1
2 def trotzierize(DeltaT, omega_s, omega_r,
3   gamma_re, delay, N, phase, Mmodes=4):
4   % ...Calculating the joint-system
   unitary U...
5   rho_srm = generateInitalStateWithDelay(
6   evuType, delay, N)
7   for t in tlist:
8     aux = generateVaccum(N)
9     rho_srme = tensor(rho_srm, aux)
10    rho_srme_Post = U*rho_srme*U.dag()
11    if Mmodes == 0:
12      if delay > 0:
13        # delay-line
14        aux_output_states = [
15        rho_srme_Post.ptrace(len(indexlist))]
16      else:
17        # white-noise
18        aux_output_states = [
19        rho_srme_Post.ptrace(1)]
20    else:
21      # ...multi-cavity...
22      rho_srm = rho_srme_Post.ptrace(
23      indexlist)

```

3.3 Ideal vs colored output

The fingerprint of the white noise measurement is a monotone rise of the measured sound. Since its frequency response is flat, it cannot contribute any further information on the frequency of the sound (whatever $\tilde{\Omega}$ assigned is the one constructed by the measurement)- in agreement to our sonification of it's output (to the input sound frequency). The output of this measurement produced a perceptually simple sound with a rapid, monotonic attack, as expected. In the case of colored noise measurement, different phases lead to different seemingly chaotic rise of excitation in the output. In constructive feedback ($\phi = \pi$) certain interaction strengths lead to oscillatory nature. We ignore at first the different frequency response- in order to compare the white and colored noise apparatuses on an equal footing-

and once again assign the excitation of the output as an envelope to the input frequency. Our first fingerprint for the color of sound - defined by the deterministic evolution of the quantum sound - is the non-monotone rise of the sound that manifests differently based on time scales: as an amplitude envelope when variations are slow compared to the sound frequency (causing volume fluctuations), or as waveform modifications when variations are fast (affecting the sound's timbre).

Our simulations were limited to the envelope "regime", as we were not able to simulate delay required for the time scale where direct manipulation on the wave form takes place (in which the measurement rate must be comparable to audible sound frequency).

In utilizing the multicavity case- by mapping the desired delay and measurement strength into a chain of (dissipated) cavities, we focus on the case of constructive feedback, in which the measurement strength assigned to each cavity is of the same size (the absolute value of the coupling- see figure 4). This model also revealed oscillatory behavior in the output of each cavity. When comparing the cavities, the resonant one yielded the highest amplitude (as expected from the theory of Leaky cavities in OQS), where cavities with different frequencies yielded amplitudes of around one order of magnitude lower. Thus, the combination of all the modes creates additional "echos" to the input sound, where these echoes have equi-distant frequencies from one another.

That leads us to the second fingerprint for the quantum color- it favors frequencies in distance proportional to the inverse of the chosen delay, and for narrow sounds it enriches the input sound with non-vanishing modes in these frequencies.

An example of the output of a certain input (sound, delay, phase and measurement strength) for each of the schemes is given in graph 5.

Figure 5: System and output auxiliary evolution for (top left) white noise apparatus and (middle top line) colored noise apparatus embodied by CM with delay. The remaining graphs show the output auxiliary of each mode of the multicavity representation of the colored noise apparatus. The physical parameters are: $\phi = \pi$, $\tau = 0.064\Omega_S$, $g = 0.8\Omega_S$ (where g is system-auxiliary coupling)

4 Outlook

We have experimented with two schemes for quantum measurement of sound, and through their comparison defined the quantum color of a sound. From which we derived three fingerprints for a Colored noise measurement-non-monotone attack, equi-distant favored frequencies, and a sort of aliasing of narrow sound to these frequencies. We highlight that the same quantum measurement schemes - our white and colored noise apparatus - can yield richer characteristics for different sonifications choices.

Though already with these definitions, an intelligible choice of the quantum delay-line parameters allows the employment of meaningful feedback and filtering, thus present our notion of "color" as a resource for sound perception. The main ingredient missing is a procedure for converting a proper sound signal into the quantum system to be measured. Among possible approaches is to sample the signal into time steps followed by discretizing the frequency representation of each time step into a multipartite quantum system. Alternatively the sound signal could be applied as a control field over the system qubit.

We conclude by noting that the random nature we've excluded is perhaps the most interesting for the development of a notion of quantum color in music. In a measurement sequence of a quantum sound (a given trajectory) the colored noise apparatus differs from the white noise apparatus by the inevitable correlations between sounds measured in intervals of the delay. These quantum correlations are no different than the Bell-correlations [1], identifying quantum information on a different footing than the classical correlations.

We intend to seek a conversion procedure of sound signal into a (composite) quantum system, with which the temporal correlations between measurement results will be imprinted in the output on temporally distant sounds in the input signal. In such a case, the color to be added introduces some rhythmic meaning to the input sound. A pair of random disturbances at a fixed temporal distance could be associated to one another in a way that cannot be gained classically². The question of whether such correlations could be noticed by a human observer, and if they could further hold aesthetic significance in a musical piece, is the motivation behind this article.

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²See for example [20], where a random output generated via quantum computing can be distinguished from another random output